

ISSN 2278-9820

National Registered & Recognized
Research Journal Related to Higher Education

VISION RESEARCH JOURNAL FOR GEOGRAPHY & GEOLOGY

REFERRED & PEER REVIEWED RESEARCH JOURNAL

Vol. II, Issue : VIII
Year - IV (Half Yearly)
(June 2015 To Nov. 2015)

Editorial Office :
'Gyandev-Parvati',
R-9/139/6-A-1,
Near Vishal School,
LIC Colony,
Pragati Nagar, Latur
Dist. Latur - 413531.
(Maharashtra), India.

Website

www.irasg.com

Contact : - 02382 - 241913
09423346913 / 09637935252
09503814000 / 7276301000

E-mail :

visiongroup@gmail.com
interlinkresearch@rediffmail.com
mbkamble2010@gmail.com

Published by :

JYOTICHANDRA PUBLICATION
Latur, Dist. Latur - 413531 (M.S.)India

Price ₹ 200/-

EDITOR IN CHIEF

Dr. Sadanand H. Gone

Principal,
Ujwal Gramin Mahavidyalaya, Ghonsi, Dist.
Latur (M.S.)India

EXECUTIVE EDITORS

Dr. A.A. Mulimani

Professor & Chairman,
Studies in Geography,
Karnataka University,
Dharwad, (K.A.)

Dr. Bhimrao S. Thombare

Head, Dept. of Geography,
Babaji Date College,
Yavatmal, Dist. Yavatmal (M.S.)

DEPUTY EDITORIAL BOARD

Dr. O. V. Shahapurkar

Head, Dept. of Geography,
Rajarshi Shahu College,
Latur, Dist. Latur. (M.S.)

Dr. A. B. Aher

Chairman, BOS Geography,
Pune University, Pune [M.S.]
Principal, Savitribai Arts College,
Pimpalgaon Pise Dist. Anagar (M.S.)

Dr. A. J. Barakade

Dept. of Geography,
K.B.P. College,
Pandharpur, Dist. Solapur (M.S.)

Dr. B. R. Phule

Head, Dept. of Geography,
Sangola College,
Sangola, Dist. Solapur

CO-EDITORIAL BOARD

Dr. T. N. Lokhande

Head Dept. of Geography,
K. S.P. College,
Pandharpur, Dist. Solapur. (M.S.)

Abhijeet R. Badade

Head, Dept. of Geography,
Late. V. D. College,
Bathalgaon, Dist. Latur. (M.S.)

Dr. Verendra Nagrale

Dept. of Geography,
S.N.D.T. University,
Pune, Dist. Pune.(M.S.)

Dr. B. N. Nagalgave

Head, Dept. of Geography,
P. D.U. College,
Deoni, Dist. Latur. (M.S.)

Vol. - II, Issue - VIII

VRJFGG

Half yearly
Research Journal

ISSN 2278-9820

June 2015 To Nov. 2015

5

DEMOGRAPHIC RISK AMONG FEMALE POPULATION IN WESTERN MAHARASHTRA : A GEOGRAPHICAL ANALYSIS

D. N. Ligade

Dept. of Geography,
Walchand College of Arts & Science,
Solapur, Dist. Solapur

Dr. G. U. Todkari

Dept. of Geography,
Walchand College of Arts & Science,
Solapur, Dist. Solapur

Research Paper - Geography

ABSTRACT

Demographic risk is as dangerous social phenomena for a people and for society as a whole. This research paper's aim to present the most significant and quantified risks in female population. For this study Western Maharashtra is selected as general and tahsils are in particular. Female population per thousand of female is continuous decreasing in Maharashtra as well as in India. Solapur District average female population is 951 per thousand male in 2011. It is uneven in tahsil and decreasing during the investigation period. For the present study, secondary data are used which is collected from socio-economic abstract of Solapur District, Sangli District, Satara District, Kolhapur District and Pune District. The collected data are analysed and represented by using statistical and cartographic techniques. Some dominant remedies suggested for increasing female population. Such type of study represents the real situation of female population in study region and also helps to planner, geographer, scientists and research students.

Keywords: demographic risk, sex ratio, demographic development,
economic dynamism

Introduction

The demographic development of an area may be defined as the demographic performance of an area in terms of pattern of life, as reflected in rural-urban component, quality of life as manifested in its literacy rates, vital rates, sex ratio and level of economic dynamism as suggested by its occupational structure. Demographic risk may be defined as an extreme social event that is dangerous or human being and society as well. The extreme consequences of demographic risks take the form of the social disasters. Female population in total population is one of the basic demographic characteristics, which is extremely vital for any meaningful demographic analysis. The numbers of females per thousand male populations refer sex ratio. The balance between the male and female population (sex ratio) is an important aspect of population structure. It reflects the underlying socio-economic and cultural patterns of a society in different ways. It directly affects on the reproductive potential of the humankind, deaths and marriages.

Objectives

The major objectives of present study are followings.

1. To measure the decadal variation of female population among rural-urban area.
2. To asses the spatial variation in female population in western Maharashtra.

Study Area

The Western Maharashtra is selected as study area. It comprises of 58 tahsils of five districts viz. Kolhapur, Pune, Satara, Sangli and Solapur district. It located from 15°45' north to 19°24' North latitudes and 73°19' East to 76°15' East longitudes. It covers an area about 57235 sq. km and it occupies 18.52 per cent total area of the Maharashtra. Krishna and Bhima river drains a large area of the central and south-eastern part of the western Maharashtra plateau through its tributaries. The soil of the district is origin from volcanic Deccan Trap. It varies from light brown to black in colour and lesser in quality. Climate of the region is generally semi-arid type expect during the monsoon season. According to 2001 census, the population of Western Maharashtra was 38,55,383. Agriculture is main occupation of the people in the district and the share of agriculture land is 62.28 percent to total geographical area.

Map No.1

Database and Methodology

Present study mostly relies on the secondary data collected through District socio-economic abstract of Solapur District, Sangli District, Satara District, Kolhapur District and Pune District in 2011. For the present investigation, District is selected as in general and tahsils in particular. The collected data are analyzed by statistical and cartographic techniques. The spatial female distribution, rural and urban female population are measured in this study.

Explanation

The Western Maharashtra is well developed part or region of Maharashtra state which consist five districts i.e. Kolhapur, Satara, Sangli, Solapur and Pune District. This region is divided in 58 tahsils. The demographic risks among female population per one thousand male are measured in Western Maharashtra. For the above objectives, the study divided into two phase.

1. Temporal Variation of Female Population
2. Spatial Variation of Female Population
1. **Temporal Variation of Female Population**

The average female population of region is 951 female behind per 1000 male. However, the temporal changes were always differing from decade to decade in rural, urban and total female population.

There is very dreadful condition of number of female population per one thousand male population in Western Maharashtra. Today, Govt. of India and many NGO's in the state, districts and tahsils have started to implements many policies and awareness campaigns to stick out this dreadful situation. The present study analyzed five decades (1961 to 2011) female population in study region.

District	Year	Female Population (per 1000 male)		
		Urban	Rural	Total
Solapur District	1961	914	975	936
	2011	961	923	942
	Change	+ 47	-52	+06
Kolhapur District	1961	885	982	970
	2011	919	965	953
	Change	+34	-17	-17
Satara District	1961	913	1065	1047
	2011	955	993	986
	Change	+42	-72	-61
Sangli District	1961	956	958	957
	2011	963	965	964
	Change	+07	+07	+07
Pune District	1961	871	992	944
	2011	899	927	910
	Change	+28	-65	-34
Region Average	1961	908	994	971
	2011	940	955	951
	Change	+32	-39	-20

Source: Socio-economic Abstract of Solapur, Sangli, Satara, Kolhapur and Pune District.

- A. Urban Female Population:** Table no -1 clearly gives an idea about the trend of female population for all five districts. The highest urban female population is 954 female per thousand male in Sangli District and lowest in Pune District i.e. 871 female in 1961. After the fifteen years, the western Maharashtra's urban female population increased 32 females and reached 940 female per one thousand male.
- B. Rural Female Population:** Female population in rural area was 994 females which decline in 2011 and reached 955 female per one thousand male. During the study period, the female population declining except Sangli District. The female population highly declining (72 female per one thousand male) in Kolhapur district

compare to other district.

- C. **Total Female Population:** The total female population western Maharashtra is 951 female per one thousand male in 2011 which was 971 female per one thousand in 1961. Although the female population declining during study period, the urban female population increased during study period and rural female population also increased in last two decades.

2. Spatial Variation of Female Population or Risk of Female Population

The spatial distribution of female population is uneven in western Maharashtra. This is happen due to the uneven situation of socio-economic as well as physical condition. The average female population of region is 951 female behind per 1000 male. This situation is dangerous for well human being. The spatial distribution of female population risk is divided in to three groups.

Table No -2

Western Maharashtra: Female Population or Risk of Female Population

Sr	Female Population	Risk of female Population	No. of tahsils	Name of tahsils
1	High (above 925)	Low Risk	47	Shahuwadi, Shirol, Bavada, Radhanagari, Kagal, Bhudargad, Ajara, Gadhinglaj, Chandgad, Junnar, Ambegaon, Shirur, Daund, Purandar, Velhe, Bor, Baramati, Indapur, Shirala, Walwa, Palus, Kadegaon, Khanapur, Atpadi, Miraj, Kavatemahankal, Jat, Wai, Khandala, Phaltan, Man, Khatav, Koregaon, Satara city, Jawali, Patan, Karad, Karmala, Madha, Barshi, North Solapur, Pandharpur, Malshiras, Sangola, Mangalwedha, South Solapur, Akkalkot
2	Medium (835-925)	Medium Risk	09	Hatkanangale, Karveer, Khed, Maval, Mulsi, Haveli, Pune City, Mahabaleshwar, Mohol,
3	Low (below 835)	High Risk	02	Panhala, Tasgaon

Source: Socio-economic Abstract of Solapur, Sangli, Satara, Kolhapur and Pune District.

- A. **Zone of Medium Female Population or Medium Risk:** Some tahsils in the study region having female population between 835 to 925 per one thousand males, these tahsils have been categorized to the zone of moderate female population in study

region. The nine tahsils of study region are lies in this zone i.e. Hatkanangale, Karveer, Khed, Maival, Mulsi, Haveli, Pune City, Mahabaleshwar and Mohol tahsil. Due to the affect of adverse physiographical location, low urbanization, traditional way of agriculture are affected the female population.

B. Zone of Low Female Population or High Risk: The female population had less than 835 females per one thousand male are included in the zone of low female population in study region. This zone is known as high risk zone of female population. The two tahsils like Panhala, Tasgaon are observed in the low female population. It is observed in Panhala due to the hilly region that's why the agriculture development and employment opportunity are low, so the more women illiteracy, high mortality rate and women's low status in family are affected on low female population. Another reason is the tahsil like Tasgaon is more employment in agriculture and agro based industries, that's why immigration of male is more from out side tahsils.

Map No.2

Conclusion

Now days, female population is 951 females per thousand male in western Maharashtra is a demographic risk. The female population is varied in urban and rural area. It is also observed that female population in urban area increased and in rural area it is decreased in last five decades. The analysis of five decades, the female population decreased in Kolhapur, Satara and Pune district and it is increased in Solapur district. The female population above 925 female per thousand male are observed in 47 tahsils of western Maharashtra. The Tasgaon and Panhala tahsils has found below 835 females per one thousand male i.e. high risk of female population.

References

1. Costela Iordache, & Cristiana Valcea (2009); "Demographic risk among female population in Romania" , Univeristy of Craiova, Vol-12, Pp-101-110.
2. Chandana R C (1989); Population Geography; Kalyani Publication NewDelhi.
3. Hussien Majid (2004); Human Geography, Rawat Publication Jaipur.
4. Majumdar Parmita (1999); Special pattern of literacy in West Bengal; Geographical review of India, Vol-61, No 2, Pp-165-172.
5. Dr. G. U. Todkari (2013): 'A Geographical Analysis of Female Population in Solapur District (MS)', Published in national seminar Barshi, ISBN-978-93-5156-812-4, Pp-144 to 149.